

**A STUDY TO EXAMINE THE INTRA
RELIABILITY OF RAPID UPPER LIMB
ASSESSMENT (RULA) IN COMPUTER
OPERATORS**

Thesis submitted to

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

in fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the Degree of

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

In Physiotherapy

By Research Scholar

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July 2019

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ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to almighty and my parents without them, achieving this milestone would not be possible.

It gives me immense pleasure to acknowledge all those who have helped me in the journey of this research. My heartfelt gratitude to **SRI. CA A. RAGHAVENDRA RAO**, President, A. Shama Rao Foundation, Mangaluru and also Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangaluru, for giving me an opportunity to progress in my career at Srinivas University and his constant motivation to excel in the field of academics. I wish to express my sincere thanks to **DR. A. SRINIVAS RAO**, Vice-president, A. Shama Rao Foundation, Mangaluru and also Pro-Chancellor, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangaluru, for his support.

I am thankful to **DR. P.S. AITHAL**, Vice-chancellor, Srinivas University. He was a constant motivator for this research.

I would like to thank my guide **Dr. SURENDRA KAMATH**, Prof in Orthopedics for his valuable guidance and expertise in the subject.

I wish to express my special thanks to **DR. RAJASEKHAR**, Dean, College of Physiotherapy Srinivas University Mangalore for his support and guidance.

I would also like to extend my gratitude to all the faculties of the college of physiotherapy, Srinivas University for their support in completing my thesis.

My thanks are due to all my mom & family members for their constant support and encouragement. A special thanks to my wife Mrs. Sonia Ajay, who motivated me and helped me throughout this work. I also thank the almighty for giving me the strength in carrying out this work.

AJAY KUMAR

ENDORSEMENT BY THE DEAN

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Introduction

1.1. INTRODUCTION

The International Labour Organization (ILO) in association with, World Health Organization (WHO) had found respect musculoskeletal issue (MSDs) as a business caused infection, which is likewise alluded to as "another plague" that ought to be inquired about and solved. MSDs affect business-related nonappearance and a high extent of days lost is expected to MSDs. Therefore, it influences the strength of workers as well as makes weight on the wellbeing framework, on the organizations monetary, and on the social expenses to manage their consequences. MSDs prevention is required in various countries to empower authorities to avoid the reactions of MSDs, improve working benefit, and reduce the weight on restorative systems at the comparable time. In creating nations like India, numerous projects for the counteractive action of MSDs have been connected to the working environment.

The business-related musculoskeletal issue is assessed to influence 4% of the absolute total populace with an expansion of 160 million new instances of business-related issue per year,⁴ as per the International Labour Office (ILO). Among them, 15% of cases are from work-place factors specific to the biomechanical factors.⁵ Overall this prompts decrease underway, non-attendance, and early retirement. Well-being is characterized as not just the nonattendance of sickness and diminished physical working, however the nearness of positive physical, mental, and psychosocial conditions of being. PCs have turned into an essential piece of workplaces and workplaces. Be that as it may, there is additionally an expanding pervasiveness of upper quadrant side effects with PC utilization. Neck and shoulder are the most vulnerable zones for creating musculoskeletal side effects among PC clients. The

adaptable hazard factors for these business associated musculoskeletal issue incorporate physical office condition and psychosocial business-related components. PC workstation format had been demonstrated to be a significant physical part of the workplace that impacts the upper quadrant symptoms. Ergonomics is a generally new idea in India yet to be viewed as a fundamental segment of most enterprises. The idea of ergonomics plays out a one of a kind job in securing human wellbeing and counteracting wellbeing risks. Introduction of movable workstations is a significant advance in the use of ergonomics. Stress on the following ergonomic principals can rapid a decrease in musculoskeletal issues and increment in the profitability of the labors.

The significance of this knowledge to plan a work environment as far as undertakings of the representative, utilizing instruments and the earth is called ergonomic structure. A decent ergonomic plan not just augments the abilities of laborers by expanding effectiveness and occupation fulfillment, yet in addition gives compensation to the organization by diminishing the expense for wellbeing and nonattendance of laborers because of wellbeing circumstances. In further wording, ergonomics ensure "appropriating the obligation to the laborer"

During earlier the 21st century most of the financial part in India is seeing an enormous change due to globalization, advancement and other overall procedures. The financial division in India has moved out through numerous changes in perspective on the way that nationalization banks occurred in 1974. In 1991 earth-shattering arrangement changes in the financial division were presented in the structure of privatization, so as to offer upgraded administrations to buyers and to help

a focused domain. Modernization and privatization strategy drove the financial portion of India to give the stimulus to change and adjustment to an upper hand in worldwide organizations as the environment.

It has been represented that there is an extended shot of making upper extremity symptoms due to the peril factors at an industrial facility. The beginning of electronic money related changes and no matter how you look at the usage of PCs and setting up of ATMs extensively are changing model of bank delegates working in India. Noteworthy changes have impacted both honestly and in an indirect manner. These are typical, financial and mental subject of bank delegates and India. These are the potential purposes behind word related weight and related issue among agents in the budgetary division of India.

The standard perspective suggests that due to inside and outside changes, agents in the budgetary section in India are going up against unusual measures of weight. Extended Perceived stress in India merchants is making them experience the evil impacts of exhaustion. A versatile work environment would influence the proficiency of individuals. Neck and shoulder torment have been seen to be connected with deferred working hours and silly sitting postures.¹⁰ Sustained sitting positions and poor workstation plans have been seen to be associated with the progress of musculoskeletal issue among PC clients. Brokers need to work for deferred lengths on PC workstations and may need to remain at work recent hours as well.

The RULA was proposed for basic use without the prerequisite for a moved degree in ergonomics or expensive apparatus. Using the RULA worksheet, the evaluator will

dole out a score for all of the going with body zones: upper arm, lower arm, wrist, neck, trunk, and legs. After the data for each region is assembled and scored, tables on the structure are then used to organize the peril factor factors, delivering a lone score that addresses the level of MSD chance as spread out underneath.

Using the RULA Assessment Tool:

The evaluator should prepare for the examination by gathering the master being surveyed to get cognizance of the movement errands and demands, and viewing the worker's improvements and positions during a couple of work cycles. Assurance of the positions to be evaluated should be established on the most irksome positions and work errands (in light of authority meeting and beginning observation), The position upheld for the longest time span, or the position where the most amazing force weights occur. The RULA can be driven quickly, so various positions and errands inside the work cycle can, by and large, be evaluated without a vital time and effort. When using RULA, simply the benefit or left side is studied immediately. In the wake of talking and viewing the pro, the evaluator can choose whether only one arm should be surveyed or if an examination is required for the different sides.

Using the RULA Assessment Tool:

The RULA worksheet is segregated into two body bit fragments on the denoted An and B. Territory A (left side) covers the arm and wrist. Territory B (right side) covers the neck, trunk, and legs. This dividing of the worksheet ensures that any gawky or constrained positions of the neck, trunk or legs which may affect the positions of the arms and wrist are consolidated into the evaluation.

The evaluator should score Group A (Arm and Wrist) first, then score Group B (Neck, Trunk, and Legs) positions for left and right. For each zone, there is a position scoring scale and additional progressions outlined on the worksheet which ought to be considered and spoke to in the score.

RULA was made to evaluate the acquaintance of individual pros with ergonomic danger segments related to furthest point MSD. The RULA ergonomic assessment mechanical assembly considers biomechanical and postural weight requirements of work assignments/demands on the neck, trunk and furthest focuses. A single-page worksheet is used to survey required body position, power, and excess. In light of the evaluations, scores are entered for each body locale in region A for the arm and wrist, and fragment B for the neck and trunk. After the data for each territory is assembled and scored, tables on the structure are then used to gather the risk factor factors, making a lone score that addresses the level of MSD possibility.

Quick Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) is an audit technique made for use in ergonomic assessments of workplaces where business-related upper member issue are represented. RULA is a screening instrument that assesses biomechanical and postural stacking by and large body with explicit thought in regards to the neck, trunk, and upper limbs.

The RULA was expected for straightforward use without the necessity for a moved degree in ergonomics or expensive equipment. Using the RULA worksheet, the evaluator will dole out a score for all of the going with body areas: upper arm, lower arm, wrist, neck, trunk, and legs. After the data for each locale is accumulated and scored, tables on the structure are then used to join the risk factor factors, creating a

single score that addresses the level of MSD chance as spread out beneath. The evaluator should prepare for the examination by gathering the authority being surveyed to get cognizance of the movement assignments and demands and viewing the worker's improvements and positions during a couple of work cycles. Assurance of the positions to be evaluated should be established on 1) the most difficult stances and work endeavors (in perspective on worker meeting and early on recognition), 2) the position proceeded for the longest time span, or 3) the position where the most imperative power weights occur. The RULA can be driven quickly, so various positions and endeavors inside the work cycle can regularly be evaluated without a significant time and effort. When using RULA, simply the benefit or left side is assessed on the double. Ensuing to talking and viewing the worker, the evaluator can choose whether only one arm should be surveyed or if an examination is required for the different sides.

The social occasion technique was changed to present the passageway plate going before riveting the can together. An establishment was made to hold the can open while the passageway plate is being presented. A straight or "in-line" pneumatic screwdriver (on an instrument balancer) is right now used to improve farthest point work acts and crash the power required. A consequent assessment using the RULA worksheet was a perpetual supply of this ergonomic technique and mechanical assembly improvement. When using the new work strategy and gadgets, the RULA full-scale score is diminished from 7 to 1.

The **REBA** is a postural examination gadget delicate to musculoskeletal risks in an arrangement of errands and evaluation of working positions found in social protection and other organizational endeavors. Performing jobs in postponed standing have contributed different prosperity impacts, for instance, business-related musculoskeletal issue, unending venous insufficiency, preterm birth, and unconstrained untimely birth, and carotid atherosclerosis. In any case, those injuries can be restricted through the utilization of structuring and legitimate controls. Nonappearance of data about ergonomics is found in the industry in which work is finished. Musculoskeletal issues are there in the welding technique where workers are working in bowing position and it exhibits that there is need to change the body positions. The use of ergonomic measures would construct machine execution and productivity, yet generally, help a human manager to be pleasing and secure. Workers work under extreme conditions to play out the perfect errand. These outrageous conditions ordinarily offer to rise to various musculoskeletal issue inside the workers. These disarrange ascend inside the worker's body due to repetitive lifting, differential lifting height, including conditions, etc. The importance of ergonomics in thing design, working condition, and its effect in mechanical workstation plan, the interdisciplinary thought of ergonomics and the consequences of ergonomics in present-day building limit.

The assessment revealed that there had been a couple of openings in the work environment, instruments, and equipment that impact the prosperity and security of workers at the worksite. Ergonomics related to the arrangement of strategies and methodology can help take out or decrease business-related threats similarly to improve the association's quality and proficiency. Ungraceful position, lifting,

directing improvement and manual work at snappy rate add to the musculoskeletal issue. Present assessment is based on assessing the work position of pro busy with different activities of tossing. The utilization of ergonomic gauges would assemble machine execution and gainfulness, yet generally, help the human manager to be pleasant and secure. It was assumed that: there is a nonattendance of ergonomics organizing and methods in little scale creating industry. A colossal degree of the workers works in horrible positions. The examination endorsed suggested that there is an urgent need of execution of ergonomics intercession with fitting care among worker essential examination of the observational data and recorded chronicles has been finished.

The **RULA** and **REBA** Score were determined to utilize Ergointelligence programming and as a representation the figuring for stance displayed. Ergointelligence programming was additionally used to check the outcomes; the information and yield screenshots of the equivalent appear in figure 2 and 3 separately. At that point, ergonomic hazard variables were distinguished by dissects the outcomes utilizing this application. The upper appendages for the most part arms and wrist of stance were surveyed utilizing RULA score sheet; the scope of development for each body site is partitioned into segments. These segments are scored so score 1 is given to the scope of development or working stance where the hazard components present are least. Higher scores are assigned to locales of the development go with progressively extraordinary stances demonstrating an expanding nearness of hazard factors causing load on the structures of the body fragment.

The introduction scores as per RULA were partitioned into four 0, 1, 2, and 3 presentation classifications: unimportant, low, medium and high separately. Medium and high hazard activities ought to be directly routed to decrease the degree of the introduction of hazard factors. For those exercises where the entire body and appendages movement should be evaluated REBA was utilized which is likewise a pen-paper strategy. In REBA the body parts are separated into areas and each body part is scored by its scope of development. Higher scores are given to the body parts where the nearness of hazard components are more and lower scores are given to those where the nearness of hazard variables are least. The REBA scores were isolated into five 0, 1, 2, 3, and 4 are classifications: irrelevant, low, medium, high and high. Medium, high and high required a quick activity to avoid any musculoskeletal issue.

Ungainly body poses while composing is related to MSDs among the PC clients. RULA (fast upper appendage appraisal) is an overview technique created for use in ergonomics examinations of work environments where business-related upper appendage issue are represented. This gadget requires no equipment in giving an energetic assessment of the positions of the neck, trunk and upper extremities nearby muscle work and the external weights experienced by the body. A coding structure is used to create a movement list which demonstrates the level of intervention required to reduce the threats of harm in light of physical stacking on the operator.¹¹ RULA is a passionate recognition system for position examination that spotlights on the chest region, anyway consolidates the lower body. It uses a movement of portrayals of different body positions, as showed up in Fig. 4.5.1, and a numerical score is distributed to the most generally perceived watched posture.¹² Group A includes the upper arm, lower arm, and wrist, and social affair B contains the neck, trunk, and legs.

The score for social event A positions and assembling B positions and the scores for static muscle work and power are added as legitimate to give a C score (upper extremity) and a D score (neck, trunk, and legs). The C and D scores are then solidified in a table to give a Grand Score. The Grand Score is used to distribute the watched position into an Action Level that exhibits the required intercession (Table 1). RULA was made as a screening instrument for an acquaintance of adults with peril factors for business-related upper extremity issue and considers the tedious improvements and power that may be required for a task. It was proposed to be done quickly and with irrelevant equipment or change to the work environment, and with inconsequential unsettling influence to those under observation. It requires no past aptitudes in observation techniques and is definitely not hard to learn.

RULA has as of late been exhibited to be reliable with adults.¹¹ Statistical checks were not disseminated but instead, the makers express that the scores demonstrated a high consistency among assessors.¹¹ RULA is seen to be significant and strong for the quick assessment of PC workers.¹³ Maintaining impeccable body position is essential for the balancing activity of MSD among these tremendous people. This examination intended to investigate the authenticity and unfaltering nature of RULA among the bank laborers' using PCs.

The position of an individual is regularly assessed in the present composition by photographic procedure or edge grabbing. Similarly, Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) is an outline procedure made for use in ergonomics assessments of workplaces where business-related upper member issue are represented. This device requires no equipment in giving an energetic assessment of positions of the neck,

trunk, and upper members nearby muscle work and the outside weights experienced by the body. A coding system is used to make a movement list which shows the level of intervention required to decrease the threats of harm due to physical stacking on the chairman. RULA was made to investigate the acquaintance of the individual pros with risk components related to business-related upper extremity issue.

The method uses blueprints of body positions and three scoring tables to give an evaluation of prologue to danger factors. The musculoskeletal issue (MSDs) can be recorded using the standard Nordic survey (SNQ). It is one of the most acclaimed outline instruments for perceiving the reality and length MSDs. Business-related MSDs have risen as a real medical issue among laborers in both industrialized and highly technological nations. Most individuals experience torment in the back, neck, and shoulder eventually, albeit few have torment over significant lots. Chronic nonspecific musculoskeletal torment is typical in young people and grown-ups, and the predominance seems, by all accounts, to be expanding. Spinal agony is a well-perceived condition related with huge individual and network troubles. The most widely recognized spinal districts contemplated are the lumbar and cervical spine, likely as a result of their solid and entrenched relationship with torment conditions, business-related wounds, intervertebral circle degenerative conditions, cerebral pains, and mental unsettling influences.

Various researchers have associated the musculoskeletal symptoms with acquaintance time with the work including body sections. A fundamental concern is that equipment should be organized by models of anthropometry, biomechanics, and neatness. The seat alone is missing for modification, and the use of the legs, feet, and back in

contact with various surfaces, similarly as solid forces are imperative to make balance. The appraisal of the match between dental seat estimations and dental expert's anthropometry revealed a noteworthy repeat of perplex especially for seat height and seat significance. Deviations from the described recognized cut off focuses changed among social events and between sexual directions indicating their unprecedented necessities and their particular potential issues.

Though various examinations have been performed to assess the ergonomic peril components looked by the dental specialists, yet there are no assessments in current composition which concentrate the effect of a range of these ergonomic factors on the MSD's in them. Additionally, systems used in the present examinations are either by observation, tape, optical or packaging grabbing. The examination of the position using RULA, which is a smart strong instrument to choose the position, has not been done in the Indian dental pro masses, demonstrating the prerequisite for the proportionate.

Quick inventive improvement in the usage of electronic data has impacted both the agents and workplace. In progressing years quick usage of PCs has changed the work environment profoundly. Various parts like individual elements, business-related factors (WRF), psycho-social segments (PSF) can achieve various prosperity hazards like musculoskeletal issue (MSD). From the composition review, it is seen that the musculoskeletal issue is exceptionally normal among PC customer's bank office laborers.

Musculoskeletal issue (MSDs) contain minor physical failures. This term is used to de-record a variety of conditions that impact the muscles, bones, and joints. The earnestness of the MSD can change. Misery and burden may intrude with standard activities. MSDs are incredibly typical, and your danger increases with age. The early finding is the best approach to straightforwardness torment while potentially decreasing further genuine damage. Quick mechanical upgrades, especially in the usage of electronic data, have affected the two authorities and the working environment (Jensen C et al,2002). Business-related MSDs can impact shoulders, arms, elbows, wrists, hands, back, legs and feet .deduced that physical and psychosocial peril segments are entangled in the etiology of MSDs especially those 6626 Rajinder Kumar Moom et al. /Procardia Manufacturing 3 (2015) 6624 – 6631,influencing the neck and shoulder locale (Akrouf et al, 2010). Jensen et al, 2002) exhibited that neck reaction was the most outstanding (53%) among female call-center workers, trailed by the shoulder (42%) and hand/wrist (30%).

The business-related musculoskeletal issue has been inspected and definite for workers from various divisions in India. These consolidate PC chairmen/reassure customers, goldsmiths, stone carvers and workers from shoe assembling plant what's progressive, woolen textiles. (Agnihotram, 2005; Mukhopadhyay and Sri-vastava, 2010; Ghosh, Das and Gangopadhyay, 2010; Bhanderi et al, 2007) Studies have evaluated the general ergonomic peril factors and effect of psychosocial workplace risk factors on occasion of musculoskeletal pain and other basic issues. Metgud et al (2008) thought about musculoskeletal similarly as respiratory issues among women workers in a woolen material mechanical office. The assessment point by point a general event of 91% for business-related musculoskeletal torment, however, did not

specify the basic conditions or territorial rate. (Gupta and Mahalanabis, 2006; Subratty and Korumtollee, 2005; Choobineh et al, 2007) Studies have examined the particular handwork in workers attracted with dull work. Gupta et al. (2006) surveyed shoe mechanical production system workers for the musculoskeletal issue, handle and press quality, and seen handicap. Notwithstanding the way that they discovered evident impairments of torment, skin changes, and decreased crush quality. Incredibly fundamental musculoskeletal diseases of thumb/wrist, for instance, carpal section issue or hand/wrist tendinitis were absent in this work bundle paying little heed to the proximity of dull advancements, solid work and ungainly Albeit various assessments have overseen MSDs among office workers in various countries, the distinct nature, and prevalence of this huge medicinal issue has not been amassed before in Punjab (India). This examination was point by point to fill the opening of data around there. The purposes of the examination were to study the ordinariness of MSDs among the PC customer bank office agents and to recognize the impact of individual, business-related and psychosocial factors on MSDs.

Whole-body Assessment (REBA)

Speedy entire body assessment (REBA) is used to study the kind of unpredictable working positions found in human administrations and other organization ventures. Data are assembled about the body present, powers used, sort of improvement or action, emphasis, and coupling. The last REBA score is made to offer a hint of the level of danger and criticalness with which movement should be taken (Hignett and McAtamney, 2000). REBA can be used when an ergonomic workplace assessment perceives that further postural examination is required and the whole body is being used. The stance is static, dynamic, rapidly changing, or unsafe. Enliven or dormant

weights are being managed either as regularly as would be prudent or conflictingly. Alterations to the workplace, equipment, getting ready, or risk-taking behavior of the worker are being checked pre/post changes.

Quick Upper Limb Assessment (RULA)

Speedy upper limb assessment (RULA) is a screening mechanical assembly that reviews biomechanical and postural stacking by and large body with explicit thought in regards to the neck, trunk, and upper members. The gadget gives a singular score as a "delineation" of the errand, which is a rating of the position, power, and improvement required. The peril is resolved into a score of 1 (low) to 7 (high). These scores are collected into four-movement levels that offer a hint of the time plot in which it is reasonable to expect risk control to be begun. RULA is used to assess the position, power, and advancement related to stationary assignments (McAtamney and Corlett, 1993). The four standard usages of RULA are to gauge musculoskeletal risk, usually as a noteworthy part of a progressively broad ergonomic assessment. take a gander at the musculoskeletal stacking of present and balanced workstation plans. survey results, for instance, gainfulness or fittingness of rigging encourage workers about musculoskeletal risk made by different working positions.

Occupational Repetitive Action (OCRA)

The word related redundant activity (OCRA) techniques to break down laborers' presentation to undertakings including different upper-appendage damage hazard elements like dreariness, power, clumsy stances what's more, developments, absence of recuperation periods (Occhipinti and Colombini, 1996). The OCRA list can be prescient of the danger of furthest point (UE) business-related musculoskeletal

disarranges (WMSDs). It is commonly utilized for the (re)design or top to bottom investigation of workstations and errands (Colombini et al., 1998, 2002). The OCRA agenda, in light of the OCRA record, is more straightforward to apply and is by and large prescribed for the underlying screening of workstations including monotonous errands (Occhipinti et al., 2000; Colombini et al., 2002).

The compact introduction record (OCRA list) is the proportion between the day by day quantities of activities as a matter of fact performed by the upper appendages in monotonous errands, to the comparing number of suggested activities (Occhipinti, 1998) scientifically it very well may be composed as, $OCRA = \frac{\text{Total number of specialized activities really performed during the move}}{\text{Total number of suggested specialized activities during the move}}$.

Ovako working stance Analysis framework (OWAS).

This strategy is utilized to investigate and control the poor work postural burden during work in ventures. By and large, the stances of Neck/head, Trunk, Arms, and legs are dissected with the help of OWAS. Furthermore, it enables the client to evaluate either the measure of weight lifted or on the other hand the quality required to play out work. Sections are likewise accommodated the season of the perception and the related work movement thus it is conceivable to interface each stance with the work movement that offered ascend to it. The strategy can be connected for the improvement of a work environment or a work strategy, to lessen its musculoskeletal burden and to make it more secure and increasingly gainful.

Visual Analog Scale (VAS)

A few examinations (Aaras et al., 2002; Carey and Gallwey, 2002, 2005; Cote et al., 2005; Khan et al., 2010a and b; Kong et al., 2011; Lin et al., 1997; You et al., 2005, Mukhopadhyay et al., 2007 and 2009; Finneran and O'Sullivan 2010 and so on.) have been found to utilize the Visual investigation scale (VAS) as a reliant variable to foresee the danger of wounds partner with WMSDs in assignments including awkward stance or insufficient power/recurrence levels. VAS is an instrument used to help an individual rate the force of specific sensations and emotions, for example, torment during working. In the examination for checking the state of torment, the visual simple scale is utilized as a flat straight line of 10 cm length with one end zero (0) which means no torment; center means moderate agony and the opposite end (10) which means the most exceedingly awful torment possible. A specialist marks a point on hold that matches the measure of torment the person feels (D'Gould et al., 2001).

Need for the study:

Musculoskeletal issue (MSDs) speak to one of the main sources of word related damage and handicap in the created and modernly creating nations. The monetary misfortune because of such issue influences the person as well as the association and the general public all in all. It has been generally acknowledged that unbalanced and compelled stances bring about the musculoskeletal weight on various body districts of situated laborers and are the main consideration in the advancement of musculoskeletal issue. Poor stances have additionally been observed to be related with diminished effectiveness of execution, a significant reason for which was perceived to be the body uneasiness coming about because of the limited stances. The Rapid upper appendage appraisal (RULA) device is one among numerous apparatuses which can

survey act among laborers. RULA is a vocation examination instrument that utilizes quantitative strategies to recognize occupations that do and don't open laborers to an expanded danger of creating furthest point and cervical disorders.¹⁴ The Rapid upper appendage appraisal helps in distinguishing proof of employments that have an expanded danger of furthest point and cervical issue, for example, average and horizontal epicondylitis, ligament ensnarement at the dorsal wrist and digits, per tendinitis, carpal passage disorder, cervical spondylitis.^{14–16} Although Rapid upper appendage evaluation technique was gotten from standards identified with physiology, biomechanics, and the study of disease transmission of furthest point and cervical issue, no investigations exist which demonstrates the test-retest capacity of RULA. Unwavering quality of a device is the ability of the instrument to duplicate past estimations of a similar object of study.¹⁷ This is typically broken into intra-and between rater dependability. Intra-rater dependability is the capacity of an apparatus to recreate estimations autonomous of when estimations are recorded.^{17,18} Intra-rater unwavering quality is otherwise called test strength or test-retest repeatability; the last equivalent word will be utilized in this investigation. The motivation behind this examination is to explore intra-rater dependability of the Rapid upper appendage appraisal instrument.

1.2. Objective of the study:

- To estimate the intra rater reliability of RULA among employees operating computers in the bank.
- To estimate inter-rater reliability RULA among the employee operating computers in the bank.
- To estimate the criterion validity of RULA against REEBA among the employees operating computers in the bank.

*Review of
Literature*

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Namwongsa et al (2018) used RULA in assessing ergonomic peril examination among the mobile phone customers. The amount of mobile phone customers all around is rapidly extending. Their assessment expected to review the level of ergonomic peril to PDA customers, and to evaluate the connection between's any self-uncovered musculoskeletal issue and the level of ergonomic risk. Thirty individuals completed a survey, altered expressly for PDA customers, to choose any musculoskeletal issue. Individuals were given an arranged phone informing undertaking and their positions were video recorded during the task. The video circumstances were surveyed by three free masters to choose the level of ergonomic danger using the Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) contraption.

RULA is an observation-based screening gadget which has been comprehensively used to overview the postural risk of IT contraption customers. Regardless, it has not yet been unequivocally utilized with wireless customers. The RULA mechanical assembly scores recognized ergonomics risks from using PDAs to content. Most phone customers had an outright RULA Grand Score of 6 for the different sides (left side: 80.00%, right side: 90.00%), exhibiting the necessity for further assessment and changes (Action Level 3). No individuals had commendable RULA Grand Scores of 1 or 2. The association between's musculoskeletal issue and the ergonomic peril among PDA customers were settled using the Chi-Square test and Fisher's cautious test; $p < 0.05$ was considered truly basic. There was a significant association between's benefit RULA Grand Score and neck musculoskeletal issue ($\chi^2 = 9.424$ at p regard = 0.009) and right RULA Grand Score and upper back musculoskeletal issue ($\chi^2 = 31.717$ at p regard < 0.001). RULA Score B (mix of neck, trunk, and leg positions)

and RULA Score D (blend of Score B, muscle use and power scores for social occasion B) were in like manner by what's more, enormous related to neck musculoskeletal issue ($\chi^2 = 19.286$ at p value < 0.001 and $\chi^2 = 9.310$ at p regard = 0.002 independently). The RULA results perceived the high ergonomics risk of phone customers, this came about in light of two key danger factors position and muscle use. The neck, trunk and leg positions joined influenced neck musculoskeletal issue. Future assessments should consider these components when arranging ergonomic interventions for mobile phone clients.

Sellschop et al (2018) considered the ergonomic direct of understudies in a deliberately decided school environment.²⁰ They fought that the PC use is extending among adolescents just like the potential for related musculoskeletal misery and postural changes. The complete effect of this advancement started, stationary lifestyle prompts poor position, torment, dull strain harm, and broken improvement plans. The inspiration driving their assessment was to develop the effect of a PC related ergonomic mediation for youngsters in a school space on position and ergonomic lead. They took all Grade 8 understudies at two indiscriminately picked educational cost based schools in Johannesburg were free to check out the examination ($n = 127$). A controlled primer differentiated a mediation gathering and a control gathering. The PC usage overview and quick upper extremity assessment (RULA) were assessed at a check, 3 and a half year post-intercession. The intercession contained a participatory informational program. An objective to-treat assessment has endeavoured. Alpha level was set at $p = 0.05$. Hypnotizing estimations (frequencies and rates) and between-pack assessment of progress, chose to differentiate in the number of individuals in the RULA action levels between get-togethers after the intervention and

the relationship of positions and kind of computer.²⁰ At a half year post-intercession, there were no individuals, all things considered, level (AL) 4 and the number of individuals in AL 3 had diminished from 26.2% at benchmark to 14.8% in the mediation gathering ($p < 0.001$). The control bundle RULA scores aggravated over the season of a half year. Regardless of the reality that the students were still not in an 'adequate' scope of postural positions, there was a noteworthy improvement between the pre-intercession and post-mediation arrange ($p < 0.001$). Their discoveries exhibit the impact of an ergonomic mediation and its manageability more than a half year. The clinical commitment of their investigation to our medicinal services framework is that through the early distinguishing proof and mediation of the poor ergonomics in a school situation, a positive effect on reducing.

Valentim et al (2018) uncovered the faithful quality, form authenticity, and interpretability of the Brazilian variation of RULA and Strain Index (SI).²¹ There are very few observational strategies for an examination of biomechanical introduction open in Brazilian-Portuguese. Their assessment wanted to differently alter and test the estimation properties of RULA and Strain Index (SI). They played out the socially different change and estimation properties test as set up as shown by Beaton et al. likewise, COSMIN rules, separately. A couple of errands that required static position and also repetitive development of upper limbs were surveyed ($n > 100$). Finally, they have reported the intra-raters' constancy for the RULA kept running from poor to basically perfect ($k: 0.00-0.93$), and SI from poor to extraordinary (ICC2.1: 0.05-0.99). The between raters' constancy was poor for RULA ($k: - 0.12$ to 0.13) and kept running from poor to coordinate for SI (ICC2.1: 0.00-0.53). The comprehension was valuable for RULA (75-100% intra-raters, and 42.24-100% among raters) and to SI

(EPM: - 1.03% to 1.97%; intra-raters, and - 0.17% to 1.51% between raters).²¹ The internal consistency was reasonable for RULA ($\alpha=0.88$), and low for SI ($\alpha=0.65$). Moderate create authenticity was seen among RULA and SI, in wrist/hand-wrist present (rho: 0.61) and quality/intensity of exertion (rho: 0.39). Along these lines, they have assumed that the balanced versions of the RULA and SI presented semantic and social equivalence for the Brazilian Portuguese.²¹ The RULA and SI had immovable quality appraisals stretched out from poor to basically immaculate. The inside consistency for RULA was better than the SI. The connection between's methods was moderate just of muscle request/improvement emphasis. Past getting ready is mandatory to use of discernments procedures for biomechanical presentation examination, notwithstanding the way that it doesn't guarantee incredible reproducibility of these measures.

Levanon et al (2014) set up the authenticity of RULA among the PC workers.¹³ According to them, the awkward body act while making is connected with a musculoskeletal issue (MSDs). A genuine quick examination of PC workers' body position is essential for the evasion of MSD among these tremendous people. Their assessment intended to take a gander at the authenticity of the adjusted brisk upper limb examination (mRULA) which adjusted the quick upper member assessment (RULA) for PC workers. Their examination broke down whether one discernment during a working day is sufficient or more observations are required. A total of 29 right-gave PC workers were chosen. RULA and mRULA were driven. The recognitions were then repeated on different occasions at one-hour between times. An imperative moderate relationship ($r = 0.6$ and $r = 0.7$ for mouse and comfort, independently) was found between the assessments. No important differences were

found between one discernment and six observations for each working day. The mRULA was seen to be considered for the examination of PC workers, and one discernment was satisfactory to assess the business-related danger factor.

Dockrell et al (2012) investigated the resolute nature of RULA as a procedure for evaluation of children's figuring posture.²² They attested that RULA is an energetic observation method for position examination. RULA has been used to overview children's PC related position, anyway, the reliability of RULA on paediatric masses has not been developed. The explanation behind their assessment was to investigate the among rater and intra-rater trustworthiness of the use of RULA with children. Video narratives of 24 more youthful understudies were independently observed by six arranged raters who assessed their positions using RULA, on two separate occasions.

RULA demonstrated higher intra-rater constancy than between rater unflinching quality though both were moderate to incredible. RULA was progressively strong when used for studying the more prepared children (8-12 years) than with the more energetic youths (4-7 years). RULA may exhibit supportive as a noteworthy part of an ergonomic assessment, anyway its level of unfaltering quality warrants alert for its sole use when looking over children, and explicitly, progressively young kids.

Bao S et al. (2007) This paper presents two-position chance assessment methodologies: introductory, an event-based procedure where the most notable and the most recognizably horrendous positions are surveyed in an endeavor; second, a period delicate methodology where position scatterings are resolved from

unpredictable instances of watched acts in the task.²³ A 'tick on-screen' present data area system was made for the time touchy position assessment strategy to make reference to the target reality process less difficult and to reduce possible position game plan tendency. The two techniques were used to gauge diverse work present parameters among an examination accomplice of 733 subjects from an arranged epidemiological examination of farthest point musculoskeletal issue. Composite position records using a changed Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) methodology were also figured using data procured by the two-position assessment systems. Results showed that the two procedures had the alternative to perceive jobs with tremendous complexities in certain position measures.

Gandavadi et al (2007) Conducted an assessment on 60 dental understudies' position on two unmistakable seats in order to choose whether one seat grades to a qualification in working posture.²⁴ RULA had the alternative to perceive that Bambach seat seats were better than standard seats. The examination was grasped at the University of Birmingham School of Dentistry in 2006. Sixty second year dental understudies.

The progression of a country depends on its industrialization. The progression of the industrialized world depends on the creation. Thusly, it might be said that the achievement of undertakings depends on gainfulness in organizations. It was felt that for the fast headway of the country setting up of new pursuits, accepting new changes in the old set up, and new progressions are significant for good working environment and faster age rate. The nineteenth-century saw broad changes in the nature and relationship of the mechanical age. Standard non-robotized establishments, skilled

worker shops were well ordered removed by capital-heightened, mechanized plants and wide division of work extended the ordinary size of firms (Chandler, 1977; Sokoloff, 1984). Productivity may be considered as the yield of product and moreover benefits per unit hypothesis of human capital. Under conditions where the essential creation depends on human productivity, must control the speedy commitment of human capital, the work-ampleness of the individual laborers, fast loss of time in view of truancy, extraordinary or perpetual infection, likewise, the whole deal loss of human capital due to early retirement or unexpected passing. The adjustments in endeavours for improved proficiency were depending on such a noteworthy number of components required by the necessities of endeavours, like modernization of organizations, showed work, improved work environment, move towards mechanical office and an extension in the ordinary length of the work year despite declining step by step significant lots of work (Atack and Bateman, 1992; Atack et al., 2002; Engerman and Goldin, 1993; Attak et al., 2003). Productivity changes with inhabitancy, feasibility, and capability. Execution normally reflects generously more than the limits, motivation, and experience of the individual delegate. Yield may be affected by nonappearance or opposition from a key accomplice, deficient organization, affiliation containments, a nonattendance of fundamental rigging or materials, powerlessness to place assets into computerization, a poor all things considered nature of the work environment, intermittent parts, or a nonattendance of purchaser demand for a thing (Shephard, 1986a and 1986b).

In earlier days, the all-inclusive community were oblivious how to control the causes accountable for affecting the effectiveness of the two recognizes increase and decrement. By then Ergonomics was displayed as a noteworthy gadget for controlling

these causes. There are strong affirmations that ergonomics additionally, gainfulness have a comfortable relationship in the industrialized world. Ergonomics as the legitimate request stressed over the perception of interchanges among individuals and different parts of a system, and the calling may apply speculation, gauges, data, and procedures to set up to redesign human success and all in all structure execution (Vink, 2006).

Ergonomics has been used to reduce the amount of work related injuries by finding those positions and errands that make basic musculoskeletal nerves. Regardless, the measures of ergonomics can be used to improve productivity as well (Resnick and Zanotti, 1997). Likewise, ergonomics redesigns realize quality and heads effectiveness (Drury, 2000; Eklund, 1995 and 1997; Battini, 2011). Convincing utilization of ergonomics in the work system setup can achieve an amicability between worker properties and undertaking demands.

This can improve worker gainfulness, give authority security and physical and mental success, additionally, work satisfaction. A couple of examinations have exhibited beneficial outcomes of applying ergonomic gauges in workplaces, machine setup, work plan, condition and workplaces plan (Hasselquist, 1981; Schanauber, 1986; Das, 1987; Rayan, 1989; Burri and Helander, 1991; Shikdar and Das, 1995; Das and Sengupta, 1996; Resnik and Zanotti, 1997; Das and Shikdar, 1999). The features of the ergonomic arrangement of machines, workstations, and workplaces are prominent. In any case, still, there is a low level of affirmation and confined application in the industry due to nonappearance of care. The crucial stress of work structure design is commonly the improvement of machines and gadgets alone anyway that isn't all, the

general errand arrangement plays gigantic employment in benefit. All things considered, incapably organized work systems were found in endeavors (Das, 1987; Konz, 1995). An ergonomically insufficient workplace can cause, Physical and energetic weight, low productivity and low nature of work (Ayoub, 1990a, b).

Productivity is generally found similarly as adequacy the number of yield units given the typical or fewer data hours. Regardless, the worker's ability or capacity to convey items or pass on organizations while encountering a business-related musculoskeletal issue (WMSD) has been outstandingly convincing in the locale of word related research related to productivity. The gainfulness makes another WMSD estimation (O'Donnell, 2000) that has made a sensible linkage among benefit and human execution, and the linkage among physical and energetic ability to work and human execution. Work proficiency as a measure has been a run of the mill subject for evaluation in various mulls over on musculoskeletal issue impacting workers (Hagberg et al., 2002; Beaton et al., 2005; Pransky et al., 2002; Lötters et al., 2005). Surprisingly, in any case, appropriated figures on recurrence and regularity related to WMSD don't generally reflect lost effectiveness and quality, enrolment and planning of substitution workers, and costs to the hurt master and the worker's family (Silverstein et al., 1998). An examination on the administration workers' cases on uttermost point issue in the United States (Feuerstein et al., 1998) found that farthest point issue was over the top to the human administrations and achieved whole deal work. Additionally, the farthest point issue spoke to an uneven bit of the pay substitution and social protection costs (Hashemi et al., 1998). In an assessment by Pransky et al. (2000), workers with lower back and uttermost focuses wounds were found to have their work execution impacted and have had related negative monetary

results. Being known to explicit components accountable for affecting the effectiveness still assessments being done to amass learning concerning basic causes which may impact productivity in association with WMSDs (Columbini and Ochipinti, 2006; Escarpizo, 2008; Korhan and Mackieh, 2010; Van der Molen et al., 2011; Finneran and O'Sullivan, 2010; Xu et al., 2012), new strategies and gadgets (Asselt et al., 2008; Attack et al., 2003; Battini et al., 2011; de korte and van Lingen, 2006; Groentjeign et al., 2004), working conditions (Dempsey et al., 2004; Frederick and Fernandez, 1999; Kahya, 2007), security of workers (Montorselli et al., 2010; Shikdar and Das, 2003a; Shikdar and Das, 2003b), task structure (Shikdar and Das, 1995; Escarpizo and Moore, 2007; Resnick and Zanotti, 1997; Vink et al., 2006), developing (Shephard, 2000), improvement of work stations (Freieling et al., 1997; Juslen et al., 2007; Yeow and Sen, 2003), new progressions (Cowan et al., 2011) and besides related to neighborhood current structure (Drucker and Feser, 2012).

Methodology

3.1 Study design

- The study design was a cross-Sectional Study, correlation study

3.2 Ethical Clearance

- Ethical clearance from Institutional Ethical Committee of Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka reference number SRNU/2008/936 dated 24.06.2008.

3.3 Study location

- State bank of India (SBI) and associated banks in Mangalore.

3.4 Study settings

- The study was conducted at the office premises of bank employees.

3.5 Study population

- Bank employees were recruited from the State bank of India (SBI) and associated banks in Mangalore

3.6 Sampling

- Simple random sampling (computer-generated random numbers)

3.7 Subject selection criteria

3.7.1 Inclusion criteria

- 25 -40 years of age, (before menopause in female).
- Male and female with normal development
- Working in computers

3.7.2 Exclusion criteria

- Impaired Vision (initially asked about the vision problem or medically pre-diagnosed child)
- Low back pain
- Any other medical, surgical and psychological conditions that prevent the child participation

3.8 Sample size

Total bank employee recruited for the study was 301.

3.9 Study duration

The data collection was done from August- 2017 to March- 2018)

3.11 Materials used for data collection

- Video camera Canon 720
- Measuring tape,(Cobra, 60 inches, 152 cm)
- Weighing machine (Krupps)
- Computer
- Computer software – Ergonomics posture analysis tool
- RULA forms and manuals

3.12. DETAILED PROCEDURE OF PRESENT WORK

Ten physiotherapists will be drawn nearer to rate digitized video reports (AVI Records) picked by the researcher to be illustrative of the PC business similarly as covering the full extent of the RULA undertaking factors. At the point when the

errand variables were doled out a rating, the evaluations were used to figure the last RULA score.

The rater buddy will contain ten physiotherapists. All individuals, paying little personality to inclusion, will be permitted an eight-hour instructional exercise on using the Rapid upper extremity examination. This included establishment on RULA measures, RULA applications, video records cases of occupations, displays on the most ideal approach to apply examinations to video archives, and an open discuss model results. Each rater was given a DVD containing 75 work video archives, a direction and approach manual. Each part was drawn closer to survey work video reports as composed by the direction manual and to use the encased structures to record task variable examinations, assessments, observations, and moreover estimations. The individuals were drawn closer to mail the structures to the experts. The second round started someplace in the scope of three and seven months after completion of cycle one. In cycle two, individuals will be requested to independently re-examine a comparable video record, repeating the technique from the hidden appraisal.

Quick Upper Limb Assessment (RULA.) scores are resolved for the position of each body part. A score of 1 exhibit the best or most fair position, e.g., arms by the sides, elbows in generally 90° flexion, wrists in fair-minded position, lower arms mid-way among pronation and supination, neck in 10° flexion, trunk and legs sitting and all around maintained. A score of 4 demonstrates the most exceedingly horrible position: e.g., shoulder flexion above 90° or flexion someplace in the scope of 45° and 90° and grabbing. The joined individual scores for shoulder, elbow and wrist gave score An

and those for neck, trunk and legs gave score B. Muscle use and power connected in every errand in the video were attributed a score of 1 and 0, independently, because they are static positions without stacking; these scores were added to scores A_n and B to obtain scores C and D, respectively.¹¹ Based on the structure of the RULA method, each blend of scores C and D (different 1-7), considered superb score and mirrors the musculoskeletal stacking related to the pro's position. While low astounding scores (of 1 or 2) exhibit that the work position is sufficient, action is proposed for the higher scores: further assessment and changes at whatever point required, for awesome scores of 3 or 4; brief assessment and changes for phenomenal scores of 5 or 6 and brisk assessments and changes for a dynamite score of 7.

3.14. Technique FOR DIGITAL VIDEOS:

Subjects are approached to wear to shorts with the goal that's a larger part of hand trunk and leg is unmistakable. It is significant that subjects should fill in as typically as could be expected under the circumstances. The camera position, or the long-range focal point, is first changed in accordance with demonstrating the entire body from the head to feet, and the subjects are recorded from the side, as they work. The entire procedure is then rehashed, with the camera acclimated to show a nearby of the body from the abdomen up. Videographs are taken in both sagittal and frontal plane.

3.15. PROCEDURE

3.15.1. Ethical statement:

The study protocol was approved from Institutional Ethical Committee of Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka reference number SRNU/2008/936 dated

24.06.2008 in correspondence with the guidelines assigned by ICMR 2017²⁸ and ground rules framed by Declaration of Helsinki (revised 2013).

3.15.2. Recruitment of participants:

An example of 301 members partook in this investigation in the wake of acquiring the earlier consent was taken from the bank specialists. Composed educated assent was gotten from every one of the members before their enrolment in this investigation. All anthropometric estimation was taken before the start of the examination including age, stature, and weight.

3.15.3. Validity:

The synchronous authenticity of RULA was developed with the premise referenced, Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA). REBA was expected for basic use without the necessity for a moved degree in ergonomics or expensive rigging. Using the REBA worksheet, the evaluator doled out a score for all of the going with body districts: wrists, lower arms, elbows, shoulders, neck, trunk, back, legs and knees. After the data for each region is assembled and scored, tables on the structure are then used to amass the danger factor factors, delivering a singular score that addresses the level of MSD shot.

3.15.4. Rater preparing and Testing:

Raters went to a 45-min instructional gathering on the use of RULA. The session joined a discussion/demonstrating using a PowerPoint prologue to exhibit RULA and specifying the circulation of the scores. This was trailed by a sensible session where

raters could watch and survey four videos fastens of bank specialist managing PCs on a planning DVD. Results were dissected and inspected until the raters felt okay with RULA. Understandings of the task of RULA scores were clarified. Following the arrangement, raters were circulated an individual time for their testing session. Raters were subjectively doled out DVD 1 or 2 depending upon the solicitation they walked around the space for the instructional course. Plenty of direct rules was given to each part before they started the testing session and a comparative strategy and show were clung to for all raters. All testing happened under similar conditions with raters arranged at a work zone 3 m from a screen onto which the video catches were foreseen. Raters were drawn nearer to assess the right-hand side position of each bank delegate. Each rater was allowed to take as much time as she required after each video fasten to complete the RULA scoring sheet. A break was offered to individuals after every eight videos fasten to balance exhaustion, as set up during the pilot period of the endeavor. The testing showed was reiterated multi-week later. Each rater saw the video cuts on an unforeseen discretionarily picked DVD in contrast with that saw during the earlier session. Rater tendency was restricted by separating the two sessions by multi-week, by using a substitute DVD for each rater in session 1 and session 2 and by how the raters were referenced to complete the RULA assessment sheet, yet the experts decided the scores at a later stage. On completion of testing the Grand Scores and the Action Levels were resolved and cross-checked by two particular analysts.

3.15.5. Reliability:

Intra-rater unwavering quality: Intra-rater dependability of RULA was set up by the essential specialist crosswise over two preliminaries on a similar gathering of

members in the equivalent natural condition and same timings for example between 10:30 a.m. - 11:00 a.m. toward the beginning of the day with a hole of 2 days.

3.15.6. Between rater unwavering quality:

Inter-rater dependability of RULA was built up by the main examiner and one other scientist (physiotherapist with five years of clinical experience) on a similar gathering of members within the equivalent ecological conditions and same timings for example between 10:30 a.m. - 11:00 a.m in the first part of the day with a hole of 2 minutes. Two experienced raters broke down autonomously 300 and one video-undertakings in a randomized request. Both the raters got preparing together. Subsequent to preparing the raters got 301 video-errands to an investigation (test) and reanalysis (retest) in discrete. Playback of the recordings should be possible as frequently as required and they could utilize a stopwatch and calculator.²¹

3.16. Information investigation

The ordinariness of gathered information was built up by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test ($n > 50$). As the information does not pursue typical circulation the unmistakable measurements of statistic attributes were communicated in mean with 95% CI, middle and range. Unwavering quality was built up by utilizing intra-class relationship coefficient ICC (3, k) for between rater dependability and ICC (2, 1) for intra-rater dependability with 95% certainty interim (CI). As per Shrout and Fleiss (1979), ICC translation < 0.5 indicates poor unwavering quality, 0.5-0.75 to be moderate dependability, 0.75-0.90 shows great unwavering quality and > 0.90 as phenomenal reliability.³⁰ The simultaneous legitimacy of RULA was built up with the basic measure, REBA test by spearman's rank relationship coefficient test ($n = 301$). For all information investigation level of centrality (LOS) was set as $p < 0.05$. Measurable examination of gathered information was performed utilizing the factual bundle of sociologies (SPSS, adaptation 20.0 Inc, Chicago, IL)

Data Analysis

Data analysis and statistics

Table 1 demonstrates the pre-characterized act classifications that were utilized in coding for the occasion based stance examination. A similar stance order framework was additionally utilized in the handling phase of the time-sensitive stance examination with the end goal of correlations with the occasion based stance examination. Truth be told, any stance order framework can Figure 1. Case of information section interface for the occasion based stance examination. The most widely recognized stance and the assessed most noticeably terrible stance of the occasion based stance investigation information were resolved independently at the undertaking level for the individual subjects and were contrasted with the relating stance parameters of the time-sensitive stance examination.

So as to get the comparing measures at the particular employment level for the occasion based act examination information, the most elevated stance gauges among numerous undertakings for each individual subject were utilized as the most exceedingly awful stances at the particular employment level. The most widely recognized stance appraisals were chosen utilizing the stance assessments relating to the longest span task. On the off chance that assignment terms were equivalent among the errands, the higher stance evaluations were utilized as the most well-known stance gauges at the specific type of employment level.

The adjusted RULA strategy used just the postural parameters of the first RULA technique (McAtamney and Corlett 1993) in the figuring. Muscle use and power/load elements were barred in this changed RULA technique. This was finished by

computing the individual RULA essential scores for the upper arms, lower arms, wrists, neck, and trunk at the errand level utilizing the occasion based stance investigation information (most normal and most exceedingly terrible stances). Since the present investigation was centered uniquely around the upper limit, leg stances were not assessed. Along these lines, the RULA leg scores were set at solidarity for both the most widely recognized and the most noticeably awful stances in the count. Utilizing these natural RULA scores, the RULA score A for the left and right half of the body and score B for the neck, trunk and legs were acquired. All RULA scores were acquired at the undertaking level for the individual subjects.

RULA scores at the errand level. The most astounding 'most exceedingly terrible' RULA score among the errands was utilized as the comparing most exceedingly awful RULA score for different errand occupations. The ceaseless stance information in the time-sensitive stance investigation was sorted utilizing the equivalent pre-characterized rakish framework as utilized in the occasion based stance examination during the post-preparing stage. The subsequent stance recurrence circulation was determined at the undertaking level for the individual subjects. Utilizing the stance recurrence circulation results, the most widely recognized stances were acquired by distinguishing the stances with most elevated recurrence of an event at the assignment level. The most exceedingly awful stance was recognized as the most exceedingly awful classified stance that was distinguished in the assignment. Since numerous pose parameters have two limits (for example outrageous wrist flexion and augmentation), a hazard level chain of importance was created and utilized in the assurance of most noticeably awful stances for the diverse stance parameters (table 1). The more prominent the hazard level score, the higher the damage, the chance for stance

classification. A comparable way to deal with that utilized in the occasion based act investigation was utilized to get the most widely recognized and most noticeably terrible stances at the chosen form of employment

level. Time-weighted averaging was utilized to process the relating stance recurrence conveyances at the specific employment level utilizing the undertaking appropriation data. The stances with the most astounding frequencies of an event at the specific employment level were chosen as the most widely recognized stances for the activity. The most exceedingly awful stances at the specific employment level were the stances of the most noteworthy hazard, which happened in any of the undertakings inside a vocation.

The adjusted RULA strategy was connected to the time-sensitive stance investigation utilizing the stances caught by every one of the dissected video outlines. These essential RULA scores at the casing level (RULA score A for left and right body sides and essential RULA scores for the assignment were utilized as the most noticeably terrible RULA scores at the undertaking level.

Comparative strategies as those utilized in the occasion based stance investigation were utilized to acquire the RULA scores at the chosen form of employment level for the time-sensitive stance investigation information. Stance disseminations, arranged to utilize the pre-characterized precise reaches, were determined for the five distinctive activity types (stationary, light, medium, overwhelming and exceptionally substantial work) for both the occasion based and the time-sensitive stance investigations at the specific type of employment level. The circulations of the changed RULA scores of the two stance investigation techniques at the chosen form of employment level were

likewise determined for the five distinctive activity types. Connection examinations were performed between the two stance investigation strategies for the ordered stance factors and adjusted RULA scores at the assignment level. Spearman's relationship coefficients were determined as a proportion of accuracy between the two strategies. The level of understanding and kappa insights looking at the two strategies were additionally determined.

Results

4. Results

All out 301 Participants who satisfied the incorporation criteria were enrolled in this investigation, where 170 members were guys, and other 131 were females. There were one missed to catch up archived. One member from the male was missing in the second day intra-rater unwavering quality session. The typicality of gathered information was authenticated by utilizing the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Definite statistic information of members incorporating mean with 95% CI, middle and range have appeared in Table 4.1. Table 4.2 showed the sex explicit statistic qualities communicated in mean with 95% CI, which shows there was a noteworthy distinction (Mann Whitney U test) of stature and weight between both the sexes. However, no importance contrast was recognized in BMI. Simultaneous legitimacy of RULA with the basis measure REBA by spearman's rank connection test was portrayed in Table 4.4 and Figure 4.6 by a disperse plot diagram, in which it was discovered that there is a huge relationship among RULA and REBA ($P < 0.001$). As indicated by Portney and Watkins criteria of making a decision about the quality it demonstrates great to a phenomenal level of direct connection among RULA and REBA. Intra-class connection coefficient (ICC) of intra-rater and between rater unwavering quality of RULA in evaluating PC laborers was expounded in Table 4.3 and Figure 4.7.1; Whereas Figure 4.7.2 showed the dependability between two sessions by the equivalent rater in estimating RULA with ICC and 95%CI, and dependability between two sessions by two diverse raters in estimating RULA with ICC and 95% CI was outlined up in Table 4.3. As indicated by Shrout and Fleiss ICC translation it demonstrates magnificent intra-rater dependability just as between rater reliability.³⁰ Figure 4.8.1 and 4.8.2 depicted the intrarater unwavering quality and interrater unwavering quality by Bland Altman chart, in both the diagram level of

understanding lies within 2SD. This affirms the Statistical techniques for surveying understanding between two strategies for clinical estimation, RULA among the PC operators.

Table 4.1: Demographic dimension of the participants recruited (n=301)

Demographic dimensions	Mean (95% CI)	Median	Range
Age (years)	38.1 (32.0-39.2)	38	24-55
Height (cm)	172.2 (171.2-173.2)	173	152-188
Weight (Kg)	80.7 (79.6-81.8)	81	58-97
BMI (Kg/m ²)	27.1 (26.9 -27.3)	27.4	20.3-28.7

Abbreviations: CI – confidence interval; cm – centimetres; kg – kilogram; BMI – Body Mass Index

Table 4.2: Demographic dimension of the male and female participants recruited.

Demographic dimensions	Male (n=170)	Female (n-131)	p-value
Age (years)	36.1 (34.7-37.4)	40.8 (39.1-42.6)	0.06
Height (cm)	178.2 (177.3-178.9)	164.5 (163.3-165.6)	<0.001
Weight (Kg)	86.9 (86.0-87.8)	72.7 (71.3-74.0)	<0.001
BMI (Kg/m ²)	27.4 (27.2-27.6)	26.8 (26.5-27.2)	0.48

Abbreviations: cm – centimeters; kg – kilogram; BMI – Body Mass Index

Table 4.3: Cronbach's alpha and intraclass correlation coefficient for Intra- rater reliability and Inter-rater reliability of RULA

Reliability	Cronbach's alpha	ICC	95% CI (ICC)
Intra- rater	0.96	0.92	0.90-0.94
Inter-rater	0.95	0.91	0.89-0.93

Abbreviations: ICC – Intra class correlation coefficient; CI – confidence interval

Table 4.4: Concurrent validity of RULA against criterion measure REBA

Concurrent validity	RULA Vs REBA	P-value
Spearman's rank correlation (ρ)	0.91	<0.001

Abbreviations: REBA - Rapid Entire Body Assessment; RULA - Rapid Upper Limb Assessment

RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet

based on RULA: a survey method for the investigation of work-related upper limb disorders, McAtamney & Corlett, Applied Ergonomics 1993, 24(2), 91-99

A. Arm and Wrist Analysis

Step 1: Locate Upper Arm Position:

Step 1a: Adjust...
 If shoulder is raised: +1
 If upper arm is abducted: +1
 If arm is supported or person is leaning: -1

Step 2: Locate Lower Arm Position:

Step 2a: Adjust...
 If either arm is working across midline or out to side of body: Add +1

Step 3: Locate Wrist Position:

Step 3a: Adjust...
 If wrist is bent from midline: Add +1

Step 4: Wrist Twist:
 If wrist is twisted in mid-range: +1
 If wrist is at or near end of range: +2

Step 5: Look-up Posture Score in Table A:
 Using values from steps 1-4 above, locate score in Table A.

Step 6: Add Muscle Use Score
 If posture mainly static (i.e. held >10 minutes), Or if action repeated occurs 4X per minute: +1

Step 7: Add Force/Load Score
 If load < 4.4 lbs (intermittent): +0
 If load 4.4 to 22 lbs (intermittent): +1
 If load 4.4 to 22 lbs (static or repeated): +2
 If more than 22 lbs or repeated or shocks: +3

Step 8: Find Row in Table C
 Add values from steps 5-7 to obtain Wrist and Arm Score. Find row in Table C.

B. Neck, Trunk and Leg Analysis

Step 9: Locate Neck Position:

Step 9a: Adjust...
 If neck is twisted: +1
 If neck is side bending: +1

Step 10: Locate Trunk Position:

Step 10a: Adjust...
 If trunk is twisted: +1
 If trunk is side bending: +1

Step 11: Legs:
 If legs and feet are supported: +1
 If not: +2

Step 12: Look-up Posture Score in Table B:
 Using values from steps 9-11 above, locate score in Table B.

Step 13: Add Muscle Use Score
 If posture mainly static (i.e. held >10 minutes), Or if action repeated occurs 4X per minute: +1

Step 14: Add Force/Load Score
 If load < 4.4 lbs (intermittent): +0
 If load 4.4 to 22 lbs (intermittent): +1
 If load 4.4 to 22 lbs (static or repeated): +2
 If more than 22 lbs or repeated or shocks: +3

Step 15: Find Column in Table C
 Add values from steps 12-14 to obtain Neck, Trunk and Leg Score. Find Column in Table C.

SCORES

Table A: Wrist Posture Score

Upper Arm	Lower Arm	Wrist Posture						
		1	2	3	4			
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3
	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3
	3	2	3	3	3	3	4	4
2	1	2	3	3	3	3	4	4
	2	3	3	3	3	4	4	4
	3	3	4	4	4	4	5	5
3	1	3	3	4	4	4	5	5
	2	3	4	4	4	4	5	5
	3	4	4	4	4	4	5	5
4	1	4	4	4	4	4	5	5
	2	4	4	4	4	4	5	5
	3	4	4	4	5	5	6	6
5	1	5	5	5	5	6	6	7
	2	5	6	6	6	6	7	7
	3	6	6	6	7	7	7	8
6	1	7	7	7	7	7	8	9
	2	8	8	8	8	9	9	9
	3	9	9	9	9	9	9	9

Table C: Neck, trunk and leg score

Wrist and Arm Score	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	1	2	3	3	4	5	5	5	5
2	2	2	3	4	4	5	5	5	5
3	3	3	3	4	4	5	6	6	6
4	3	3	3	4	5	6	6	6	6
5	4	4	4	5	6	7	7	7	7
6	4	4	4	5	6	7	7	7	7
7	5	5	6	6	7	7	7	7	7
8+	5	5	6	7	7	7	7	7	7

Task name: _____ Reviewer: _____ Date: ____/____/____ provided by Practical Ergonomics
 This tool is provided without warranty. The author has provided this tool as a simple means for applying the concepts provided in RULA. © 2004 Nease Consulting, Inc. rbarker@ergosmart.com (816) 444-1667

Figure 4.5.1: Rapid Upper Limb Assessment (RULA) employee assessment worksheet

REBA Employee Assessment Worksheet

Based on Technical note: Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA), Hignett, McAtamney, Applied Ergonomics 31 (2000) 201-205

A. Neck, Trunk and Leg Analysis

Step 1: Locate Neck Position

 Step 1a: Adjust...
 If neck is twisted: +1
 If neck is side bending: +1

Step 2: Locate Trunk Position

 Step 2a: Adjust...
 If trunk is twisted: +1
 If trunk is side bending: +2

Step 3: Legs

 Adjust: 30-60° Add +1, >60° Add +2

Step 4: Look-up Posture Score in Table A
 Using values from steps 1-3 above, locate score in Table A.

Step 5: Add Force/Load Score
 If load < 11 lbs: +0
 If load 11 to 22 lbs: +1
 If load > 22 lbs: +2
 Adjust: If block or rapid build up of force: add +1

Step 6: Score A, Find Row in Table C
 Add values from steps 4 & 5 to obtain Score A. Find Row in Table C.

Scoring:
 1 = negligible risk
 2 or 3 = low risk, change may be needed
 4 to 7 = medium risk, further investigation, change soon
 8 to 10 = high risk, investigate and implement change
 11+ = very high risk, implement change

B. Arm and Wrist Analysis

Step 7: Locate Upper Arm Position:

 Step 7a: Adjust...
 If shoulder is raised: +1
 If upper arm is abducted: +1
 If arm is supported or person is leaning: -1

Step 8: Locate Lower Arm Position:

Step 9: Locate Wrist Position:

 Step 9a: Adjust...
 If wrist is bent from midline or twisted: Add +1

Step 10: Look-up Posture Score in Table B
 Using values from steps 7-9 above, locate score in Table B

Step 11: Add Coupling Score
 Well fitting Handle and mid range power grip: good: +0
 Acceptable but not ideal hand hold or coupling acceptable with another body part: fair: +1
 Hand held not acceptable but possible: poor: +2
 No handles, awkward, unsafe with any body part: Unacceptable: +3

Step 12: Score B, Find Column in Table C
 Add values from steps 10 & 11 to obtain Score B. Find column in Table C and match with Score A in row from step 6 to obtain Table C Score.

Step 13: Activity Score
 +1 1 or more body parts are held for longer than 1 minute (static)
 +1 Repeated small range actions (more than 4x per minute)
 +1 Action causes rapid large range changes in postures or unstable base

Table A		Table C											
		Score B, (table B value + coupling score)											
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Legs	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	
Trunk Posture Score	1	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	3	3	5	6
	2	2	3	4	5	3	4	5	6	4	5	6	7
	3	2	4	5	6	4	5	6	7	5	6	7	8
	4	3	5	6	7	5	6	7	8	6	7	8	9
5	4	6	7	8	6	7	8	9	7	8	9	10	

Table B		Lower Arm					
		Wrist					
		1	2	3	4		
Upper Arm Score	1	1	2	2	1	2	3
	2	1	2	3	2	3	4
	3	3	4	5	4	5	5
	4	4	5	5	5	6	7
	5	5	6	7	6	7	8
	6	7	8	8	8	9	9

Table C												
Score A (score from Table A + load/force score)	Score B, (table B value + coupling score)											
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	
1	1	1	1	2	3	3	4	5	6	7	7	7
2	1	2	2	3	4	4	5	6	6	7	7	8
3	2	3	3	3	4	5	6	7	7	8	8	8
4	3	4	4	4	5	6	7	8	8	9	9	9
5	4	4	4	5	6	7	8	8	9	9	9	9
6	6	6	6	7	8	8	9	9	10	10	10	10
7	7	7	7	8	9	9	9	10	10	11	11	11
8	8	8	8	9	10	10	10	10	11	11	11	11
9	9	9	9	10	10	10	11	11	11	12	12	12
10	10	10	10	11	11	11	11	12	12	12	12	12
11	11	11	11	11	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12

Table C Score

+

Activity Score

Final REBA Score

Task name: _____ Reviewer: _____ Date: ____/____/____
 This tool is provided without warranty. The author has provided this tool as a simple means for applying the concepts provided in REBA. © 2004 Jones & Bartlett, Inc. provided by Practical Ergonomics
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Figure 4.5.2: Rapid Entire Body Assessment (REBA) employee assessment worksheet

Figure 4.6: Scatter plot describing the association between RULA and REBA

Figure 4.7.1: Scatter plot portraying the intra-rater reliability of RULA among bank employees

Figure 4.7.2: Scatter plot portraying the inter-rater reliability of RULA among bank employees

Figure 4.8.1: The Bland Altman graph shows LOA in intra-rater reliability of RULA

Figure 4.8.1: The Bland Altman graph shows LOA in inter-rater reliability of RULA

Discussion

5. Discussion:

In this examination the legitimacy and unwavering quality of RULA is set up. The aftereffect of the investigation exhibited that RULA is observed to be substantial and solid among bank specialists. RULA has great simultaneous dependability with REBA, Table 5 and fantastic intra-rater and inter-rater unwavering quality among sessions and ratters from Table 4. To best of our insight, this article is the principal report of legitimacy and unwavering quality among bank representatives by RULA. The purpose of executing this examination among the bank representatives is that the worker spent practically the most extreme piece of working hours before PCs or workstations. The situation of the PC while being utilized is a significant indicator for creating musculoskeletal torment as this identifies with the idea of ergonomic behavior.²⁰ Working extended periods without lay on a workstation or PC puts an impressive strain on the position of trunk and neck flexion with hyperextension of the upper cervical spine.

Routine stances may get influenced straightforwardly by PC use. Notwithstanding utilizing PC for exceptionally low spans could have a destroying impact on stance which may cause the lasting changes in the routine stance through transient postural changes. Other factors, for example, poor social working may prompt both more prominent measures of PC use and changes in stance which may impact the PC use while we considering the ongoing stance As the PC use has a causal impact on constant stance, the long haul consequences for the musculoskeletal framework is of potential our worry. A large number of the progressions in postural edges related with PC use were reliable crosswise over various sitting conditions. For instance, more

prominent PC use was identified with more noteworthy lumbar expansion in females when looking forward, looking down, and drooped sitting. This pattern most likely identifies with an abnormal state of the relationship between spinal edges over these three unmistakable sitting positions in the two folks and females. Regardless, these affiliations would, by and large, endure when standing. The connection between head flexion and PC use in folks that was found in the sitting position resembled that seen during standing. Moreover, the connection between lumbar point and PC use in females found in the sitting position resembled that seen during standing. These unflinching affiliations demonstrate that PC use may apply an effect on progressing spinal stances.

PC use could in like manner impact steady positions by suggestion, as physical activity or torment. Unusual measures of PC use may incite diminished physical development, with the following lessening in muscle persistence that could impact consistent stance. High degrees of PC use may extend neck torment.

There are five elements which may impact the relentless nature of this assessment. They were the work, the worker, the technique, the rater and the time. The variables that may have impacted clearly faithful quality was time (test-retest) and the experience of the raters, in spite of the way that it that attested that experience rater level add to tremendous differentiation in the RULA scores. On the other hand, the raters were extraordinary comprehension for the majority of the methods in the middle of rater assessment using RULA.

Levanon et al (2014) revealed that mRULA was found to have moderate to the great level of ($r=0.6-0.7$) simultaneous legitimacy for the evaluation of PC workers. This is less substantial when contrasted with our aftereffects of a good level of simultaneous legitimacy ($\rho=0.91$) of RULA against REBA. Thus moderate to great level of developing legitimacy ($r=0.69$) against overhauled Upper Extremity Work Demand (UEWD-R) Scale³⁵ and strain list ($\rho=0.61$).

The intra-raters' unflinching quality for the Brazilian variation RULA went from poor to for all intents and purposes perfect ($k: 0.00-0.93$) while the between raters' constancy was very poor for RULA ($k: - 0.12$ to 0.13).²¹ Good test-retest steadfastness of ICC = 0.79 was represented by Cavalini et al.

RULA displayed the rooftop sway only a little over the farthest point of 10%. This discovering demonstrates that the technique has certain inconvenience in perceiving the level of peril presentation between the high-chance endeavors, and may interfere in the gathering for fundamental administration concerning the brief or conceded intercession. Everything considered this is the first assessment to display the authenticity and the relentless nature of RULA among the bank laborers.

Validity and Reliability:

Proof of endorsement of REBA instrument was given by Hignett and McAtamney (2000) where between observers immovable quality between the 14 individuals for coding was seen to be someplace in the scope of 62 and 85%. Janowitz et al. (2006) found that between observer unflinching quality is moderate except for the neck and

upper members. Face authenticity was polished in two phases; the main included coding 144 position blends by three ergonomists and joining the honing thoughts of weight, coupling and development scores to deliver the last REBA score (1-15), with related peril and movement

levels and the ensuing stage included 14 specialists for the gathering and individual coding of in excess of 600 examples of positions from human administrations, control and manufacturing organizations (Hignett and McAtamney,2000; Stanton et al., 2004). Farsighted authenticity, that is the way by which well the hazard estimation of the procedure has been exhibited to be related to or on the other hand anticipating musculoskeletal issue, was shown by Jones and Kumar (2010) that unassuming degrees of understanding between strategies explored affirm hazard level yield will rely upon the technique utilized and there is an important danger of contradiction between strategies. The outcomes of their examination avow the compelled comprehension between circulated ergonomic peril assessment strategies Dima Al Madani and Awwad Dababneh/American Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences.what's more, the necessity for concentrates prepared to take a gander at the judicious authenticity of the systems in a comparative worker people to show the present best model. The consequence of this logical inconsistency is the mixed up examination of danger just as unmistakable evidence of issue exposures.

To the extent synchronous authenticity; how well the system relates with progressively generous procedures, a couple of examinations used REBA to differentiate the results and other observational and direct methodologies to decide the degree of comprehension between the two. Various examinations (Joseph et al., 2011;

Jones and Kumar, 2010, Kee and Karwowski, 2007; Jones and Kumar, 2010; Coyle, 2005) present results standing out two from five methodologies for reviewing WMSDs peril. With the exception of Kee and Karwowski (2007) study, where OWAS, REBA and RULA systems are considered using data from a case of 301 positions gotten from various present-day parts, relationships are generally made using test estimates that are pretty much nothing and furthermore from a lone workplace (e.g., Jones and Kumar, 2010).

Kee and Karwowski (2007) paper, REBA showed up the most raised intra-rater unflinching quality among OWAS and RULA.

The connection results for RULA and REBA seem more understanding than that obtained by Kee and Karwowski (2007). These makers declared 48% consistency, as appeared differently in relation to 73.7% in Chiasson et al. (2012) study. The complexities between the activity levels and danger arrangements used can be the clarification behind the assortment.

Using comparative danger classes as Chiasson et al. (2012) study, Jones and Kumar (2010) conveyed 66% congruity among RULA and REBA, regardless of the way that with an uncommonly little model (four workstations in the identical mechanical division).

A high random occasion between the two procedures was shown by De Sa et al. (2006).

REBA discernments have contrasted sensibly with those of the OWAS system as demonstrated by Takala et al. (2010), regardless of the way that REBA gathered more positions to have an increasingly raised measure of risk. No reports on association with the musculoskeletal issue were found. For leg and trunk positions, between intrarater repeatability was moderate to extraordinary anyway low for upper limbs. Limitations Being an observational assessment gadget, REBA is a conceptual procedure; it needs detail and exactness and spreads three noteworthy risk factors: Force, repetition what's more, demonstration. Coyle (2005) and Janowitz et al. (2006) exhibited that

A couple of factors (e.g., turning, parallel bending, grabbing) are weighted correspondingly by REBA regardless to what degree they exist (e.g., 5° winding or 20° of turning). As demonstrated by Coyle (2005), REBA is time using; the "most detectably awful position" contrasts depending upon the body part being surveyed.

The data for the benefit and left hand can't be joined so they ought to be surveyed autonomously; the customer needs to pick what to watch (e.g., positions requiring the most solid activity, practically once in a while repeated positions, or positions known to cause the most burden). Length and repeat of things are not considered; the nonattendance of a period delicate measures in REBA prompts 'the most ordinary' positions and the high commitment cycle positions being situated the equal (David, 2005; Chiasson et al., 2012; Shanahan et al., 2013; Jones and Kumar, 2010; Takala et al., 2010). Concentrates kept an eye on agreeing that no technique has been found legitimate for all applications. An all out appraisal of WMSDs chance in the workplace ought to be done using multiple strategies. A workstation can have danger

factors that a couple of systems don't consider; the extent of percent understanding between occupations suggests that the methods differ in their sensibility to the presentation profiles of different occupations.

5.1. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- 1) Unavoidable human error during the measurement of RULA and REBA.
- 2) Reference norms should be extrapolated with cautious as the data was collected from a single city.

5.2. STRENGTH OF THE STUDY

- 1) RULA is less expensive flexibility measure tool, can easily administer in any field setting where expensive sophisticated equipment is not available.
- 2) RULA required minimal training and can be implemented without difficulty.

5.3. FURTHER RECOMMENDATIONS

- 1) Further, the RULA can extend over among the specially-abled population.
- 2) This test can also be performed among patients with musculoskeletal and neurological disorders after the modifications.

5.4. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

- 1) RULA will be helpful in screening flexibility in early childhood assessing the ergonomic level among the computer operators.
- 2) Helpful in documenting improvement in ergonomic parameters over a period.

Conclusion

6. Conclusion

This investigation has inferred that RULA is a dependable device, which can be utilized in PC laborers particularly bank representatives. RULA is likewise indicating magnificent simultaneous legitimacy with REBA.

RULA assessment recommends the snappy execution of ergonomics intercessions with authentic data among workers and prosperity guidance on ordinary postural change, execution, and seeing of laws among organizations are endorsed to cut down word related danger because of musculoskeletal issue.

Summary

SUMMARY:

Different musculoskeletal issue (MSD) side effects can be experienced by the laborers playing out their assignments in awful work stances which are to a great extent static and thus these are related with long haul dangers and wounds. These stances additionally badly affect work execution and work efficiency. In such manner, this contextual analysis research work has been led in a chosen earthenware manufacturing plant of Bangladesh with the point of assessment of work stances of laborers working in the creative segment of the plant through fast upper appendage appraisal (RULA) and their effect on work efficiency. The auxiliary goal of the exploration work was to draw an examination of related dangers with the terrible work act. So as to assess the work stances of laborers, RULA method has been utilized. RULA is a broadly utilized apparatus produced for the appraisal of work stances which explicitly analyzes the degree of hazard related with the upper appendage issue of individual laborers by scoring the diverse body district of the laborers. The outcomes got from this examination work have been plotted into three principal segments, in particular, the recognizable proof of positive or negative work pose and the degree of dangers related with poor work stance and their effect on work efficiency. It has been distinguished that most specialists have been presented to the upper appendage uneasiness which thus adds to the danger of wounds during the presentation of work. Through the examination of RULA, it has been uncovered that no stance is discovered hazard free during the examination of work stances of laborers. As per RULA fabulous score of 7, 43.59% of the laborers need prompt examination and changes demonstrating that the degree of presentation to postural dangers is extremely high and quick ergonomics intercession to diminish the introduction to hazard level appear to be basic. The outcome of the terrible work

stance brings about the musculoskeletal issue (MSDs) which have additionally been examined in this exploration work. The most ordinarily influenced body districts found among the 39 recorded specialists are shoulders (92.31%), neck (71.79%), wrist (71.31%), lower back (43.59%) and upper back (41.03%). In conclusion, the relationship between's RULA stupendous score and work profitability has appeared. The graphical investigation uncovers that there is a diminishing pattern of work efficiency with the higher RULA fantastic score setting up the way that there exists an opposite connection between normal RULA terrific score and normal work profitability.

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Appendix

Annexure - 1

[Informed Consent form for the computer operators]

This Informed Consent Form is for men and women who are working in the bank and using computers during maximum working hours in State Bank of India and who we are inviting to participate in research on Reliability and Validity Study. The title of our research project is **"A study to examine the intra reliability of rapid upper limb assessment (RULA) in computer operators."**

Name of Principal Investigator: Ajay Kumar

Name of Organization: Srinivas College of physiotherapy & research center,
Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru-1

Name of Proposal: A study to examine the intrarater reliability of rapid upper limb assessment (RULA) in computer operators.

This Informed Consent Form has two parts:

- Information Sheet (to share information about the research with you)
- Certificate of Consent (for signatures if you agree to take part)

You will be given a copy of the full Informed Consent Form

PART I: Information Sheet

Introduction

I, Ajay Kumar, working for the Srinivas College of physiotherapy & research center, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru. We are doing research on establishing the validity and reliability of RULA (rapid upper limb assessment) among the computer. I am going to give you the information and invite you to be part of this research. You do not have to decide today whether or not you will participate in the research. Before you decide, you can talk to anyone you feel comfortable with about the research.

There may be some words that you do not understand. Please ask me to stop as we go through the information and I will take time to explain. If you have questions later, you can ask them of me, the study doctor or the staff.

Purpose of the research

Awkward body posture while typing is associated with musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) among computer users. RULA (rapid upper limb assessment) is a survey method developed for use in ergonomics investigations of workplaces where work-related upper limb disorders are reported. This tool requires no special equipment in providing a quick assessment of the postures of the neck, trunk and upper limbs along with muscle function and the external loads experienced by the body. A coding system is used to generate an action list which indicates the level of intervention required to reduce the risks of injury due to physical loading on the operator. RULA is a subjective observation method of posture analysis that focuses on the upper body

but includes the lower body. Their applicability to the bank employees is obsolete. Hence there is a need to develop and validate the scale to be used among the Indian. The reason we are doing this research is to find out the validity and the intrarater reliability of RULA in computer operators.

Type of Research Intervention

This research will involve a single administration of validated scales of RULA during visits to your working area, State Bank of India, Mangalore, Karnataka

Participant selection

We are inviting all the bank employee from State Bank of India, Mangaluru, Karnataka using computers during working hours.

Voluntary Participation

Your participation in this research is entirely voluntary. It is your choice whether to participate or not. Whether you choose to participate or not, all the services you receive from the bank will continue and nothing will change. If you choose not to participate in this research project, you will not be involved in our research, and we will tell you more about it later. You may change your mind later and stop participating even if you agreed earlier.

Information RULA testing phase

The RULA used in this research is in reliability and validity testing phase. There are no known side effects/problems or risks.

Procedures and Protocol

During the research, you make two visits to the clinic.

- In the first visit, the employee working with computers will be evaluated with RULA and REBA, standardized criterion measure to establish the concurrent validity. We will also ask you a few questions about your general health and measure how tall you are and how much you weigh.
- At the next visit, which will be within two weeks, you will again be evaluated with the RULA. Then will be asked some questions about your health.

Duration

The research takes place over 2 days in total. During that time, it will be necessary for you to come to the hospital for 2 days, for 30 minutes to one hour each day.

Side Effects

As already mentioned, as this will be an assessment scale, no known side effects are associated with RULA but can have some unwanted effects. It can make you tired during the performance of the test. It is possible that it may also cause some problems that we are not aware of. However, we will follow you closely and keep track of any

unwanted effects or any problems. We may stop the use of RULA and REBA if you feel uncomfortable.

Risks

By participating in this research it is possible that you will be at greater risk than you would otherwise be. There is, for example, a risk of loss of attention during the working hours due to the video recordings of RULA. While the possibility of this happening is very low, you should still be aware of the possibility. We will try to decrease the chances of this event occurring, but if something unexpected happens, we will provide you with free treatment.

Benefits

If you participate in this research, you will have the following benefits: any interim illnesses will be treated at concession charge to you. There may not be any benefit for you but your participation is likely to help us find the answer to the research question. There may not be any benefit to the society at this stage of the research, but future generations are likely to benefit.

Reimbursements

You will not be given any other money or gifts to take part in this research.

Confidentiality

With this research, something out of the ordinary is being done in your community. It is possible that if others in the community are aware that you are participating, they may ask you questions. We will not be sharing the identity of those participating in the research.

The information that we collect from this research project will be kept confidential. Information about you that will be collected during the research will be put away and no-one but the researchers will be able to see it. Any information about you will have a number on it instead of your name. Only the researchers will know what your number is and we will lock that information up with a lock and key. It will not be shared with or given to anyone except [name who will have access to the information, such as research sponsors, DSMB board, your clinician, etc.

Sharing the Results

The knowledge that we get from doing this research will be shared with you through community meetings before it is made widely available to the public. Confidential information will not be shared. There will be small meetings in the community and these will be announced. After these meetings, we will publish the results in order that other interested people may learn from our research.

Right to Refuse or Withdraw

You do not have to take part in this research if you do not wish to do so. You may also stop participating in the research at any time you choose. It is your choice and all of your rights will still be respected.

Alternatives to Participating

If you do not wish to take part in the research, you will be provided with the established standard treatment available at the center/institute/hospital. People who have knee osteoarthritis are given

Who to Contact

If you have any questions you may ask them now or later, even after the study has started. If you wish to ask questions later, you may contact any of the following: Dr. Ajay Kumar, Srinivas College of physiotherapy & research center, Srinivas University, Pandeshwar, Mangaluru, Karnataka/telephone number/e-mail.

This proposal has been reviewed and approved by Srinivas University Ethics Committee, which is a committee whose task it is to make sure that research participants are protected from harm. It has also been reviewed by the Ethics Review Committee of the World Health Organization (WHO), which is funding/sponsoring/supporting the study.

PART II: Certificate of Consent

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions that I have asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to participate as a participant in this research.

Print Name of Participant _____

Signature of Participant _____

Date _____

Day/month/year

If illiterate

A literate witness must sign (if possible, this person should be selected by the participant and should have no connection to the research team). Participants who are illiterate should include their thumb-print as well.

I have witnessed the accurate reading of the consent form to the potential participant, and the individual has had the opportunity to ask questions. I confirm that the individual has given consent freely.

Print name of witness _____
participant

AND Left Thumb print of

Signature of witness _____

Date _____

Day/month/year

I, Dr. Ajay Kumar have accurately read out the information sheet to the potential participant, and to the best of my ability made sure that the participant understands the details on the information sheet.

I confirm that the participant was given an opportunity to ask questions about the study, and all the questions asked by the participant have been answered correctly and to the best of my ability. I confirm that the individual has not been coerced into giving consent, and the consent has been given freely and voluntarily.

A copy of this Informed Consent Form (ICF) has been provided to the participant.

Print Name of Researcher/person taking the consent: Dr. Ajay Kumar

Signature of Researcher /person taking the consent _____

Date _____

Day/month/year

Annexure – 2

Master Chart

S.No	Age	Sex	Height	Weight	RULA_1	RULA_2	RULA_3	REBA	BMI
5.	31.00	1.00	167.00	76.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	27.25
6.	34.00	1.00	178.00	89.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	28.09
7.	28.00	1.00	186.00	97.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	28.04
8.	27.00	2.00	157.00	66.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	26.78
9.	39.00	2.00	168.00	77.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	27.28
10.	45.00	1.00	181.00	93.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	28.39
11.	30.00	1.00	173.00	82.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.40
12.	29.00	2.00	165.00	74.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.18
13.	44.00	1.00	171.00	82.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.04
14.	51.00	2.00	169.00	58.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	20.31
15.	33.00	1.00	175.00	86.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
16.	37.00	2.00	152.00	63.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	27.27
17.	26.00	1.00	180.00	91.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	28.09
18.	28.00	1.00	176.00	87.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.09
19.	32.00	1.00	177.00	88.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	6.00	28.09
20.	41.00	2.00	161.00	70.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	27.01
21.	50.00	1.00	179.00	92.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	28.71
22.	48.00	2.00	159.00	71.00	4.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
23.	46.00	1.00	182.00	79.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	23.85
24.	38.00	1.00	188.00	96.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	27.16

25.	52.00	2.00	167.00	74.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	26.53
26.	45.00	1.00	184.00	83.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	24.52
27.	30.00	2.00	158.00	66.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	26.44
28.	27.00	1.00	174.00	81.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	26.75
29.	49.00	2.00	167.00	78.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	27.97
30.	51.00	1.00	182.00	90.00	7.00	6.00	7.00	9.00	27.17
31.	55.00	2.00	178.00	89.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	28.09
32.	24.00	2.00	171.00	80.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.36
33.	48.00	2.00	166.00	78.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	28.31
34.	25.00	1.00	176.00	85.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.44
35.	31.00	1.00	167.00	76.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	27.25
36.	34.00	1.00	178.00	89.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	28.09
37.	28.00	1.00	186.00	97.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	28.04
38.	27.00	2.00	157.00	66.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	26.78
39.	39.00	2.00	168.00	77.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	27.28
40.	45.00	1.00	181.00	93.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	28.39
41.	30.00	1.00	173.00	82.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.40
42.	29.00	2.00	165.00	74.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.18
43.	44.00	1.00	171.00	82.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.04
44.	51.00	2.00	169.00	58.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	20.31
45.	33.00	1.00	175.00	86.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
46.	37.00	2.00	152.00	63.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	27.27
47.	26.00	1.00	180.00	91.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	28.09
48.	28.00	1.00	176.00	87.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.09

49.	32.00	1.00	177.00	88.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	6.00	28.09
50.	41.00	2.00	161.00	70.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	27.01
51.	50.00	1.00	179.00	92.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	28.71
52.	48.00	2.00	159.00	71.00	4.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
53.	46.00	1.00	182.00	79.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	23.85
54.	38.00	1.00	188.00	96.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	27.16
55.	52.00	2.00	167.00	74.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	26.53
56.	45.00	1.00	184.00	83.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	24.52
57.	30.00	2.00	158.00	66.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	26.44
58.	27.00	1.00	174.00	81.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	26.75
59.	49.00	2.00	167.00	78.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	27.97
60.	51.00	1.00	182.00	90.00	7.00	6.00	7.00	9.00	27.17
61.	55.00	2.00	178.00	89.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	28.09
62.	24.00	2.00	171.00	80.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.36
63.	48.00	2.00	166.00	78.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	28.31
64.	25.00	1.00	176.00	85.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.44
65.	31.00	1.00	167.00	76.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	27.25
66.	34.00	1.00	178.00	89.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	28.09
67.	28.00	1.00	186.00	97.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	28.04
68.	27.00	2.00	157.00	66.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	26.78
69.	39.00	2.00	168.00	77.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	27.28
70.	45.00	1.00	181.00	93.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	28.39
71.	30.00	1.00	173.00	82.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.40
72.	29.00	2.00	165.00	74.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.18

73.	44.00	1.00	171.00	82.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.04
74.	51.00	2.00	169.00	58.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	20.31
75.	33.00	1.00	175.00	86.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
76.	37.00	2.00	152.00	63.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	27.27
77.	26.00	1.00	180.00	91.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	28.09
78.	28.00	1.00	176.00	87.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.09
79.	32.00	1.00	177.00	88.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	6.00	28.09
80.	41.00	2.00	161.00	70.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	27.01
81.	50.00	1.00	179.00	92.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	28.71
82.	48.00	2.00	159.00	71.00	4.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
83.	46.00	1.00	182.00	79.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	23.85
84.	38.00	1.00	188.00	96.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	27.16
85.	52.00	2.00	167.00	74.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	26.53
86.	45.00	1.00	184.00	83.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	24.52
87.	30.00	2.00	158.00	66.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	26.44
88.	27.00	1.00	174.00	81.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	26.75
89.	49.00	2.00	167.00	78.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	27.97
90.	51.00	1.00	182.00	90.00	7.00	6.00	7.00	9.00	27.17
91.	55.00	2.00	178.00	89.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	28.09
92.	24.00	2.00	171.00	80.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.36
93.	48.00	2.00	166.00	78.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	28.31
94.	25.00	1.00	176.00	85.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.44
95.	31.00	1.00	167.00	76.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	27.25
96.	34.00	1.00	178.00	89.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	28.09

97.	28.00	1.00	186.00	97.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	28.04
98.	27.00	2.00	157.00	66.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	26.78
99.	39.00	2.00	168.00	77.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	27.28
100.	45.00	1.00	181.00	93.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	28.39
101.	30.00	1.00	173.00	82.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.40
102.	29.00	2.00	165.00	74.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.18
103.	44.00	1.00	171.00	82.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.04
104.	51.00	2.00	169.00	58.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	20.31
105.	33.00	1.00	175.00	86.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
106.	37.00	2.00	152.00	63.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	27.27
107.	26.00	1.00	180.00	91.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	28.09
108.	28.00	1.00	176.00	87.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.09
109.	32.00	1.00	177.00	88.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	6.00	28.09
110.	41.00	2.00	161.00	70.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	27.01
111.	50.00	1.00	179.00	92.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	28.71
112.	48.00	2.00	159.00	71.00	4.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
113.	46.00	1.00	182.00	79.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	23.85
114.	38.00	1.00	188.00	96.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	27.16
115.	52.00	2.00	167.00	74.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	26.53
116.	45.00	1.00	184.00	83.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	24.52
117.	30.00	2.00	158.00	66.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	26.44
118.	27.00	1.00	174.00	81.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	26.75
119.	49.00	2.00	167.00	78.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	27.97
120.	51.00	1.00	182.00	90.00	7.00	6.00	7.00	9.00	27.17

121.	55.00	2.00	178.00	89.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	28.09
122.	24.00	2.00	171.00	80.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.36
123.	48.00	2.00	166.00	78.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	28.31
124.	25.00	1.00	176.00	85.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.44
125.	31.00	1.00	167.00	76.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	27.25
126.	34.00	1.00	178.00	89.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	28.09
127.	28.00	1.00	186.00	97.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	28.04
128.	27.00	2.00	157.00	66.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	26.78
129.	39.00	2.00	168.00	77.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	27.28
130.	45.00	1.00	181.00	93.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	28.39
131.	30.00	1.00	173.00	82.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.40
132.	29.00	2.00	165.00	74.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.18
133.	44.00	1.00	171.00	82.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.04
134.	51.00	2.00	169.00	58.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	20.31
135.	33.00	1.00	175.00	86.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
136.	37.00	2.00	152.00	63.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	27.27
137.	26.00	1.00	180.00	91.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	28.09
138.	28.00	1.00	176.00	87.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.09
139.	32.00	1.00	177.00	88.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	6.00	28.09
140.	41.00	2.00	161.00	70.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	27.01
141.	50.00	1.00	179.00	92.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	28.71
142.	48.00	2.00	159.00	71.00	4.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
143.	46.00	1.00	182.00	79.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	23.85
144.	38.00	1.00	188.00	96.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	27.16

145.	52.00	2.00	167.00	74.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	26.53
146.	45.00	1.00	184.00	83.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	24.52
147.	30.00	2.00	158.00	66.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	26.44
148.	27.00	1.00	174.00	81.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	26.75
149.	49.00	2.00	167.00	78.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	27.97
150.	51.00	1.00	182.00	90.00	7.00	6.00	7.00	9.00	27.17
151.	55.00	2.00	178.00	89.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	28.09
152.	24.00	2.00	171.00	80.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.36
153.	48.00	2.00	166.00	78.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	28.31
154.	25.00	1.00	176.00	85.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.44
155.	31.00	1.00	167.00	76.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	27.25
156.	34.00	1.00	178.00	89.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	28.09
157.	28.00	1.00	186.00	97.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	28.04
158.	27.00	2.00	157.00	66.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	26.78
159.	39.00	2.00	168.00	77.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	27.28
160.	45.00	1.00	181.00	93.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	28.39
161.	30.00	1.00	173.00	82.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.40
162.	29.00	2.00	165.00	74.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.18
163.	44.00	1.00	171.00	82.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.04
164.	51.00	2.00	169.00	58.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	20.31
165.	33.00	1.00	175.00	86.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
166.	37.00	2.00	152.00	63.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	27.27
167.	26.00	1.00	180.00	91.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	28.09
168.	28.00	1.00	176.00	87.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.09

169.	32.00	1.00	177.00	88.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	6.00	28.09
170.	41.00	2.00	161.00	70.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	27.01
171.	50.00	1.00	179.00	92.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	28.71
172.	48.00	2.00	159.00	71.00	4.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
173.	46.00	1.00	182.00	79.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	23.85
174.	38.00	1.00	188.00	96.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	27.16
175.	52.00	2.00	167.00	74.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	26.53
176.	45.00	1.00	184.00	83.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	24.52
177.	30.00	2.00	158.00	66.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	26.44
178.	27.00	1.00	174.00	81.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	26.75
179.	49.00	2.00	167.00	78.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	27.97
180.	51.00	1.00	182.00	90.00	7.00	6.00	7.00	9.00	27.17
181.	55.00	2.00	178.00	89.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	28.09
182.	24.00	2.00	171.00	80.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.36
183.	48.00	2.00	166.00	78.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	28.31
184.	25.00	1.00	176.00	85.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.44
185.	31.00	1.00	167.00	76.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	27.25
186.	34.00	1.00	178.00	89.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	28.09
187.	28.00	1.00	186.00	97.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	28.04
188.	27.00	2.00	157.00	66.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	26.78
189.	39.00	2.00	168.00	77.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	27.28
190.	45.00	1.00	181.00	93.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	28.39
191.	30.00	1.00	173.00	82.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.40
192.	29.00	2.00	165.00	74.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.18

193.	44.00	1.00	171.00	82.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.04
194.	51.00	2.00	169.00	58.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	20.31
195.	33.00	1.00	175.00	86.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
196.	37.00	2.00	152.00	63.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	27.27
197.	26.00	1.00	180.00	91.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	28.09
198.	28.00	1.00	176.00	87.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.09
199.	32.00	1.00	177.00	88.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	6.00	28.09
200.	41.00	2.00	161.00	70.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	27.01
201.	50.00	1.00	179.00	92.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	28.71
202.	48.00	2.00	159.00	71.00	4.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
203.	46.00	1.00	182.00	79.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	23.85
204.	38.00	1.00	188.00	96.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	27.16
205.	52.00	2.00	167.00	74.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	26.53
206.	45.00	1.00	184.00	83.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	24.52
207.	30.00	2.00	158.00	66.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	26.44
208.	27.00	1.00	174.00	81.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	26.75
209.	49.00	2.00	167.00	78.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	27.97
210.	51.00	1.00	182.00	90.00	7.00	6.00	7.00	9.00	27.17
211.	55.00	2.00	178.00	89.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	28.09
212.	24.00	2.00	171.00	80.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.36
213.	48.00	2.00	166.00	78.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	28.31
214.	25.00	1.00	176.00	85.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.44
215.	31.00	1.00	167.00	76.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	27.25
216.	34.00	1.00	178.00	89.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	28.09

217.	28.00	1.00	186.00	97.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	28.04
218.	27.00	2.00	157.00	66.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	26.78
219.	39.00	2.00	168.00	77.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	27.28
220.	45.00	1.00	181.00	93.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	28.39
221.	30.00	1.00	173.00	82.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.40
222.	29.00	2.00	165.00	74.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.18
223.	44.00	1.00	171.00	82.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.04
224.	51.00	2.00	169.00	58.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	20.31
225.	33.00	1.00	175.00	86.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
226.	37.00	2.00	152.00	63.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	27.27
227.	26.00	1.00	180.00	91.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	28.09
228.	28.00	1.00	176.00	87.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.09
229.	32.00	1.00	177.00	88.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	6.00	28.09
230.	41.00	2.00	161.00	70.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	27.01
231.	50.00	1.00	179.00	92.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	28.71
232.	48.00	2.00	159.00	71.00	4.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
233.	46.00	1.00	182.00	79.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	23.85
234.	38.00	1.00	188.00	96.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	27.16
235.	52.00	2.00	167.00	74.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	26.53
236.	45.00	1.00	184.00	83.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	24.52
237.	30.00	2.00	158.00	66.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	26.44
238.	27.00	1.00	174.00	81.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	26.75
239.	49.00	2.00	167.00	78.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	27.97
240.	51.00	1.00	182.00	90.00	7.00	6.00	7.00	9.00	27.17

241.	55.00	2.00	178.00	89.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	28.09
242.	24.00	2.00	171.00	80.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.36
243.	48.00	2.00	166.00	78.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	28.31
244.	25.00	1.00	176.00	85.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.44
245.	31.00	1.00	167.00	76.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	27.25
246.	34.00	1.00	178.00	89.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	28.09
247.	28.00	1.00	186.00	97.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	28.04
248.	27.00	2.00	157.00	66.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	26.78
249.	39.00	2.00	168.00	77.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	27.28
250.	45.00	1.00	181.00	93.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	28.39
251.	30.00	1.00	173.00	82.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.40
252.	29.00	2.00	165.00	74.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.18
253.	44.00	1.00	171.00	82.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.04
254.	51.00	2.00	169.00	58.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	20.31
255.	33.00	1.00	175.00	86.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
256.	37.00	2.00	152.00	63.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	27.27
257.	26.00	1.00	180.00	91.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	28.09
258.	28.00	1.00	176.00	87.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.09
259.	32.00	1.00	177.00	88.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	6.00	28.09
260.	41.00	2.00	161.00	70.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	27.01
261.	50.00	1.00	179.00	92.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	28.71
262.	48.00	2.00	159.00	71.00	4.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
263.	46.00	1.00	182.00	79.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	23.85
264.	38.00	1.00	188.00	96.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	27.16

265.	52.00	2.00	167.00	74.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	26.53
266.	45.00	1.00	184.00	83.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	24.52
267.	30.00	2.00	158.00	66.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	26.44
268.	27.00	1.00	174.00	81.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	26.75
269.	49.00	2.00	167.00	78.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	27.97
270.	51.00	1.00	182.00	90.00	7.00	6.00	7.00	9.00	27.17
271.	55.00	2.00	178.00	89.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	28.09
272.	24.00	2.00	171.00	80.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.36
273.	48.00	2.00	166.00	78.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	28.31
274.	25.00	1.00	176.00	85.00	6.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.44
275.	31.00	1.00	167.00	76.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	27.25
276.	34.00	1.00	178.00	89.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	28.09
277.	28.00	1.00	186.00	97.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	28.04
278.	27.00	2.00	157.00	66.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	26.78
279.	39.00	2.00	168.00	77.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	27.28
280.	45.00	1.00	181.00	93.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	8.00	28.39
281.	30.00	1.00	173.00	82.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	27.40
282.	29.00	2.00	165.00	74.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	6.00	27.18
283.	44.00	1.00	171.00	82.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.04
284.	51.00	2.00	169.00	58.00	4.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	20.31
285.	33.00	1.00	175.00	86.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
286.	37.00	2.00	152.00	63.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	27.27
287.	26.00	1.00	180.00	91.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	28.09
288.	28.00	1.00	176.00	87.00	6.00	6.00	6.00	7.00	28.09

289.	32.00	1.00	177.00	88.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	6.00	28.09
290.	41.00	2.00	161.00	70.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	27.01
291.	50.00	1.00	179.00	92.00	5.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	28.71
292.	48.00	2.00	159.00	71.00	4.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	28.08
293.	46.00	1.00	182.00	79.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	23.85
294.	38.00	1.00	188.00	96.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	27.16
295.	52.00	2.00	167.00	74.00	6.00	6.00	5.00	6.00	26.53
296.	45.00	1.00	184.00	83.00	7.00	7.00	7.00	9.00	24.52
297.	30.00	2.00	158.00	66.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	26.44
298.	27.00	1.00	174.00	81.00	4.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	26.75
299.	49.00	2.00	167.00	78.00	5.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	27.97
300.	51.00	1.00	182.00	90.00	7.00	6.00	7.00	9.00	27.17
301.	55.00	2.00	178.00	89.00	4.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	28.09

SRINIVAS COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY & RESEARCH CENTRE

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08 February 2019

Mr.AJAY KUMAR has presented his Ph.d synopsis titled “A STUDY TO EXAMINE THE INTRA RELIABILITY OF RAPID UPPER LIMB ASSESMENT (RULA) IN COMPUTER OPERATORS” before the Institutional Ethical committee. The Ethical committee has approved and permitted him to proceed with the protocol further.

ETHICAL COMMITTEE CHAIRPERSON